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Cell type-specific activation of cyclin dependent kinases in response to CDK4/6 inhibition.

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CDKs exhibit functional specificity likely associated with specific roles for separate CDKs. CDK inhibition for clinical intervention will be accompanied by CDK activation whose expression dynamics (type and quantity of CDK activated as a compensatory measure) are likely cell-type specific. We measured total transcription in separate cellular systems modeling pharmacologic inhibition of the cyclin dependent kinases CDK4/6.